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D6.1 Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

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List of Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Funded under European Union's **Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Investment Programme**, the **RAISE project** will provide the infrastructure for a distributed crowdsourced data processing system, moving from open data to open access data for processing. The project aims at promoting a transparent way of sharing and processing data, enabling the research community to publish their work with evidence-based authenticity of the data-analysis performed, ensuring at the same time the accreditation of their work.

The current document with the title "*D6.1 Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan*" is divided into **two main parts**. The **first part** (*chapter 2 and 3*) defines the communication and dissemination strategy of the project, outlines the methods, tools and channels to be employed throughout the project's duration, describes the actions that partners will undertake and specifies the audience that the activities will be addressed to. It also includes a **Calendar** of communication and dissemination activities that stem from the Grant Agreement and a tentative **Action Plan** where partners expressed their intentions for performing such actions.

The **second part** (*chapter 4*) includes the exploitation plan which will direct project partners' related efforts for defining RAISE solution's end users ("*consumers*" of RAISE services) and potential investors ("*buyers*" of RAISE services); determine their needs and meet them where possible via targeted services; specify the RAISE results and examine potential market uptake; define the foreground knowledge produced and protect the intellectual property of RAISE partners (*individually and as a whole*); update partner's individual plans related to the results produced by them during the project's implementation; and overall ensure the sustainability of the RAISE solution in long term (*beyond the completion of the EU funding*). A **Timeline of Actions** (*divided to project's yearly quarters*) along with the techniques to be employed is also enclosed as pathway to RAISE's sustainability.

D6.1 is a public deliverable of this project, part of WP6 and includes information about the project's scope as well as a short description of WP6 in order to ensure that no prior knowledge related to the project, the DoA and the other WP6 deliverables is requested from the reader. Overall, it is based on, and is consistent with the DoA and the GA, but is not a substitute for reading these documents.

1 Introduction

1.1 The RAISE Project

The mission of **RAISE** is to provide the infrastructure for a distributed crowdsourced data processing system, moving from open data to open access data for processing. RAISE will provide the mechanism for sending the algorithm to the dataset instead of sending the data to the algorithm. The real value of open data for the research community is not to access them but to process them as conveniently as possible to reduce time-to-result and increase productivity. **RAISE** aims at promoting a transparent way of sharing and processing data, enabling the research community to publish their work with evidence-based authenticity of the data-analysis performed, ensuring at the same time the accreditation of their work.

RAISE will be grounded on the fundamental principle defined in the **FAIR Guiding Principles** for scientific data management and stewardship (*Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability*). To do so, RAISE brings the processing algorithm (*small size*) to the dataset (*large size*) instead of downloading the dataset to the computer where the processing algorithm is. To increase the processing capacity of the dataset repositories, RAISE borrows the crowdsourcing concept where researchers can easily integrate in the existing workflows computers serving both their datasets and the processing capacity.

1.2 WP6: Dissemination, Exploitation, Sustainability and EOSC Integration

The objectives of this work package are: **i)** *to raise awareness within participants, target groups and the European society at large about the existence of RAISE, its objectives, progress and results;* **ii)** *to prepare and launch training courses and materials for researchers;* **iii)** *coordination with relevant projects, (pilot theme) data spaces and the EOSC association, to coordinate developments and align with roadmaps, avoiding duplicities;* **iv)** *integration of identified EOSC services reuse and provision of RAISE as EOSC service.*

The sixth work package is divided into **8 tasks** which namely are:

- **Task 6.1:** Dissemination and Communication plan (*task leader: VILABS*)
- **Task 6.2:** Exploitation and Sustainability (*task leader: VILABS*)
- **Task 6.3:** Awareness towards the general public, the research community and policy makers (*task leader: VILABS*)
- **Task 6.4:** Training courses and Materials (*task leader: OPENAIRE*)
- **Task 6.5:** Innovation Monitoring, Open-Source Licensing and Community building (*task leader: VILABS*)
- **Task 6.6:** Coordination with relevant projects and data repositories (*task leader: VILABS*)
- **Task 6.7:** EOSC services reuse and RAISE as EOSC service (*task leader: VILABS*)
- **Task 6.8:** Journal submission system RAI Integration (*task leader: AUTH*)

1.3 The Deliverable D6.1

1.3.1 Purpose and Scope

The strategy to be followed for performing the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities of RAISE along with related plans for dissemination and exploitation respectively is of utmost importance for ensuring the effectiveness of such actions. It should be stressed that this deliverable will serve as a **reference point** for project partners towards the planned actions, assist the consortium to monitor the activities realization and update it accordingly when and where necessary based on the project's needs.

D6.1 defines in a clear manner the approach that will be followed and establishes a common understanding amongst the consortium. Overall, the expected result of this deliverable is to achieve significant awareness of the initiative, active engagement of the necessary stakeholders; and ensure the sustainability of the RAISE results beyond the EC funding.

1.3.2 Methodology followed

The **methodology** followed for the formation of the current overall plan was based upon the close and constructed collaboration of **WP6 leader** with all partners. The initial version was created by **VILABS** and it was circulated via email to the consortium for reviewing and commenting. It was finalized after incorporating all comments / suggestions received.

In brief, the steps taken were:

- **Phase 1:** Creation of a **WP6 Questionnaire** (see section 1.3.3) by **VILABS** which assisted partners to form and express their individual plans.
- **Phase 2:** Each project partner was contacted through email by VILABS and requested for contribution (*filling in the questionnaire*).
- **Phase 3:** Collection of partners' individual plans and views by VILABS.
- **Phase 4:** Evaluation and **consolidation** of the available input by VILABS.
- **Phase 5:** Circulation to the consortium of plan's final version by VILABS and **final approval** provided by consortium.

Figure 1: Methodology followed

1.3.3 WP6 Questionnaire

Within the context of WP6 activities which include communication, dissemination and exploitation aspects, VILABS team as leader of this work package, conducted an internal survey amongst the RAISE partners in order to draft the frame in which the consortium will conduct such actions given the obligations that stem from the Grant Agreement.

The main idea behind the creation of this survey was to ensure that all project partners would be able to express their plans, views and thoughts in a structured manner at their own pace. Thus, VILABS formulated a series of questions tailored to the project's topic and needs and selected the adequate tool for building it. The **WP6 Questionnaire** was created at the **EU survey tool** after examining several options that are available online for such cases. Lastly, the EU survey was chosen due to several reasons such as reliability (*in terms of operation*), ease of use, range of features, secure environment from cyber-attacks and its respect to GDPR rules. The link of the questionnaire is publicly available mainly for reporting purposes, but it can also be utilized as a best practice for other EU funded projects and initiatives.

WP6 Questionnaire link at the EU survey:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/62068c3e-f7a7-6ae3-4f76-fdb9e1ca07e3>

The required time for answering all questions included therein was estimated to **15 minutes approximately**. The WP6 Questionnaire is divided into **six parts** which namely are:

- **Part A - Participation in Conferences & other Events:** RAISE partners were asked to select from a list of events the ones that they were planning or had interest to participate / attend. Moreover, partners were able to fill in / suggest other events not included in that list.
- **Part B – Publications:** RAISE partners were requested to express their intentions for contributing to the scientific publications of the project. The option to suggest and name potential topics for publication was also available to partners.
- **Part C - Organization of RAISE outreach event:** RAISE partners were requested to reply about their intentions and thoughts around the organization of project's outreach events.
- **Part D - Channels, Tools and Network:** RAISE partners were asked to insert at the related fields the channels, tools and networks that their organization can use to promote the project.

D6.1 Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

- **Part E - Key Messages:** RAISE partners were requested to suggest any key messages per target audience.
- **Part F - Pathway to Exploitation:** RAISE partners were asked to contribute to a S.W.O.T. analysis related to the project.

Each part of WP6 Questionnaire included an explanatory text for assisting partners to better express their view and navigate throughout survey's questions. A preview of it (*screenshot*) is provided in **Figure 2**.

RAISE Project | Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

RAISE Questionnaire | Partners Contribution

Introduction

By this survey VILabs is collecting your view in order to formulate the consolidated Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of the RAISE project. Moreover, aspects on Exploitation actions are examined for formulating the related Strategy.

Notation: The information extracted by this survey will be included in the public deliverable of WP6 under the title **DS.1 "Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan"** (RAISE).

Partner's Information

Please, insert the name of your organization and your name. The name of your organization and your Name will be included in the contributors list of the Deliverable **DS.1**. In case of any clarification needed in regards to the input you have provided, VILabs team will contact you. Please note that no emails of the contributors will be included in **DS.1**.

Q1. Organization (please, insert the Name of your Organization)

Q2. Name (please, insert your Name)

Part A: Participation In Conferences & other Events

You are kindly requested to fill in which conferences / events are you planning to participate. Moreover, you may indicate your intention to participate by selecting the respected option.

Q3. Which of the following conferences / event are you planning to participate?

Conferences / Events	YES	NO	Express your Interest / Intention
Open Science Conference When: 21-23 Sep. 2023 Where: Online More at: https://www.open-science-conference.eu/	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open Science FAIR When: 25-27 September 2023 Where: Madrid, Spain More at: https://www.opensciencefair.eu/	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
18th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and innovations When: 14-17 June 2023 Where: Lezh, Spain & Hybrid More at: https://ijaaai.org/2023/	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AAAI Conferences of 2024 and / or 2026 (upcoming) When: TBD Where: TBD More at (when available): https://aaai.org/	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
International Conference on Recent Innovations in Computer Science, Engineering and Technology When: 2-3 December 2023 Where: Scotland, UK More at: http://scienceplus.iee/Conference/25698101923c1/	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
18th European Conference on Artificial Intelligence When: 30 Sept. - 5 Oct. 2023 Where: Krakow, Poland More at: https://ecai2023.eu/	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 2: WP6 Questionnaire (preview)

1.3.4 Intended Readership

This deliverable is primarily addressed to RAISE consortium for establishing a **common understanding** on communication, dissemination and exploitation actions of the project and utilize its content as a *“handbook”* when needed. Furthermore, D6.1 is an **official document** of the project the funding authority (*European Commission / REA*) is considered as a significant audience for reading it. A detailed analysis of the intended audiences is provided in the **table 1**.

Intended Audience	Reasons for interest in reading
RAISE project partners	To establish a common understanding amongst the consortium towards the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities to be performed and particularly the strategy to be followed; the tools, channels and methods to be used; the execution time; and the requested contribution.
European Commission / REA	The current deliverable constitutes an official one of the RAISE project. The European Commission as the funding authority shall assess the planned activities and the quality of the document.
Target Groups and potential end users	To be informed about the project in general; its scope; the dissemination and exploitation activities that are planned to be performed during the RAISE lifecycle and detect the channels from where they can acquire the project's results.
EOSC Community	To be informed about the dissemination and exploitation activities planned by the RAISE consortium and, if possible, to support and /or engage in such actions for providing their feedback. Knowledge exchange can be further encouraged via the current plan as it includes significant information such as tools, methods and channels to be employed by RAISE and the time of execution is defined which might lead to more common actions.
Representatives of organizations involved in EU funded projects under similar topic	To be informed about best practices, gain knowledge and lessons learned that might find them useful in the implementation of their dissemination and exploitation activities. In addition, it can assist in introducing the project into similar ones and lead in possible communication and dissemination synergies by identifying opportunities for future joint actions.
Anyone interested (<i>general public</i>)	To be informed about the project's topic and its scope; the strategy and means that will be utilized to promote the RAISE and its outputs; and the manner to sustain the project's results beyond its lifecycle.

Table 1: Intended Readership

1.3.5 Structure of the deliverable

D6.1 is comprised of **5 chapters** and **4 appendices**. The **first chapter** is an introductory one where the RAISE project is presented in brief and a short WP6 description is provided. In addition, it includes the scope of the deliverable, the audience that is addressed to, its relation to other WP6 deliverables and the methodology followed for its creation. The **second chapter** describes the dissemination strategy of the project (*objectives, target audience, tools, channels, metrics etc.*) and the **third one** outlines the RAISE communication and dissemination plan. The **fourth chapter** delineates the exploitation plan of the project, and the **fifth one** concludes this document.

Regarding appendices, **Annex 1** includes partners' communication channels and networks to be employed for supporting RAISE's related actions; **Annex 2** encloses the communication and dissemination action plan (*detailed list*); **Annex 3** contains the dissemination request template; and **Annex 4** the reporting template for the communication and disseminations actions.

1.3.6 Relationship with other RAISE deliverables

As WP6 actions are interlinked, the deliverable D6.1 is related with the other WP6 deliverables and the table below describes such dependencies and relations.

WP6 Deliverables	Dependencies and Relation
D6.2 Communication Dissemination and Exploitation progress report (first version)	D6.2 will provide a report about the overall progress of all WP activities with emphasis on the activities performed, lessons learnt and an updated planning for the final period. The strategy and the plan presented in D6.1 will define the approach to be followed and the actions to be taken.
D6.3 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report (final version)	D6.3 will provide a report about the overall progress of the WP, with emphasis on the activities performed, on the benefits of the various stakeholders involved, the synergies developed with existing initiatives, the roadmap for expansion and the guide for replication of research and services. It will also describe the RAISE plan, the integration with EOSC and the performed activities for final deployment and sustainability. D6.1 will define the approach to be followed and the actions to be taken while D6.2 will provide an update to the plan presented in D6.1.

Table 2: Relation of D6.1 with other WP6 deliverables

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The purpose of the **Communication and Dissemination Strategy** (*C. & D. Strategy*), described in the current chapter, is to provide an overall framework as well as guidelines for the successful implementation of all communication and dissemination activities. It aims to ensure that those actions are aligned with the overall goals of the project as well as the interrelated ones that stem from the rest WPs. The main goal of the C & D strategy is to achieve high visibility of the project to stakeholders and widespread of RAISE produced results to target audiences in order to engage them for receiving valuable feedback.

Figure 3: Elements of RAISE Communication & Dissemination Strategy (C & D. Strategy)

The RAISE C. & D. Strategy is consisted of **seven main elements** which namely are: **Objectives**; **Target Audience**; **Channels and Tools**; **Messages**; **Rules and Obligations**; **Action Plan**; and **Metrics**. It concerns **all work packages** of the project, thus RAISE partners are requested to align all their related actions such as organization of RAISE outreach events, attendance / participation to third party events, scientific publications authorship and so on accordingly with this strategy.

As mentioned in the GA, the involvement of all work packages is required for presenting their findings, assist in creating a positive reputation around the project and interlink their results with the exploitation action. The **four goals** of a successful communication and dissemination activity are:

- i. Identification of the **dissemination** and **communication activity**.
- ii. Identification of the **communication objectives**.
- iii. Identification of the **target groups**.
- iv. Determination of the **information** to be provided - The message.

Thus, the effective dissemination strategy shall be answering the following questions: **a) Why?** (*Reasons for dissemination*), **b) What?** (Information to be disseminated) **c) How?** (*Tools and Channels*); **d) Who?** (*Consortium partner/s*); **e) When?** (*Time*); **f) To Whom?** (*Categories of Audience*); and **g) Where?** (*Location*).

Questions	Description
Why? (Reasons for dissemination)	The reasons for dissemination are consisted of: the contractual obligation of the consortium; demonstrate the research work performed by the project partners during the implementation of RAISE; transfer the produced results to follow-up initiatives; receive feedback from the users; and prepare the ground for the exploitation actions in order to ensure the sustainability of the produced results.
What? (Information to be disseminated)	The information to be shared are consisted of: - Project achievements: Anything that has been achieved and how it was achieved. As examples can be considered the completion of deliverables, tasks, milestones, project events (<i>hackathons, workshops, final conference etc.</i>), face-to-face meetings with VIPs, mass media references to the project with major impact. - Project results such as public deliverables, data, knowledge, good practices, methodologies applied for implementing and delivering the project results - Lessons learned (<i>bad or good ones</i>): Anything related to the project that is useful for third parties to become aware and either endorse or avoid.
How? (Tools, channels and networks)	The tools, channels and networks to convey the RAISE messages. For example, via the project's website, e-newsletters issues, project's social media accounts, publications in peer-reviewed journals, conference papers, articles / interviews in mass media, press releases, face-to-face meetings with end-users and target groups, participation in third party events (<i>conferences, workshop, trade fairs, EC events, exhibitions etc.</i>), promotional materials and so on.
Who? (Consortium partners)	The project partner/s to be involved in the implementation of the activities and have undertaken either to lead it or contribute together with the rest of the consortium.
To Whom? (Categories of audience)	The audience that will be reached out and includes: stakeholders; industries; universities and research centers; EOSC community, potential end users; decision makers.
When (Time)	The execution time of the activity during project's lifecycle.
Where? (Location)	The place (<i>location</i>) where the activity will occur.

Table 3: Rationale of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Objectives

The objectives defined that will assist in the successful planning on communication and dissemination are:

- Widely and effectively communicate the project's objectives and its relevant findings / achievements.
- Create and maintain a large and specialized network of stakeholders which includes experts.
- Push project outcomes to market.

- Organize RAISE events, workshops, datathons and meetings for disseminating the project's results to target audiences.
- Through the RAISE outreach events to engage the target audiences and collect valuable feedback by them.
- Link with other EU funded project, particularly EOSC ones, for strengthening collaboration with relevant research organizations, businesses and public authorities.
- Create positive reputation around the project and its offered solution.
- Raise the profile of the organizations carrying out the project at local, national and international level so as to highlight the European added value of activities supported by the Horizon Europe programme.
- Transfer the research-based knowledge to the ones that can make use of it (*end users*).

2.2 Target Audience Identification

Since the proposal phase, the consortium has worked towards identifying the target audiences i.e. to whom the dissemination and communication actions will be directed. So, the main efforts will be put to **i) researchers data providers** (*including RIs, clusters, long tail of science*); **ii) researchers data processors**; **iii) industry** (*companies with algorithms*); **iv) publishers**; **v) open data repositories**; **vi) policy makers**; **vii) EOSC community**.

It should be noted that the **European Commission** as the funding authority as well as the **general public** are also considered as a significant segment of target audiences.

2.3 Analysis of Methods, Tools and Channels

Every strategy is implemented by specified methods, tools and channels in order to achieve the desired results. The same framework applies to the RAISE communication and dissemination strategy thus the methods that will be employed are: **publications** (*conference proceedings, journals*); **face-to-face activities** (*including virtual ones*) such as events, workshops, meetings, demonstrations and so on; **online activities** which include the project's website, e-newsletters, **invitations** via email direct distribution; **press-based activities** i.e. press releases, TV or radio interviews, articles on press (*including online media*); direct distribution of **paper-based promotional materials** (*brochures, factsheets, posters*) in events, meetings, workshops etc.; and establishing **collaborations** (*liaisons*) with similar projects, initiatives and organizations.

After citing the methods, the tools that consortium will employ are:

- **E-newsletter issues** will be published throughout the project's lifecycle.
- **Factsheet** and **brochure** in printable format for distribution in all kinds of events and face-to-face meetings with stakeholders. Moreover, a **poster** will be created for using it during RAISE outreach activities. It should be noted that the digital format of those promotional materials will be available at RAISE website.
- **Press releases** for announcing to target audience as well as to general public the most important achievements of the consortium. All press releases will be published in English and, if necessary, they will be translated in partner's language for achieving the maximum visibility.
- **RAISE presentations** in all types of events to communicate project's results and increase its visibility to target audience. Public presentations with non-confidential will be available at project's website.
- **Videos**: audio-visual material will be produced during the project's implementation aiming to promote the project and communicate its results.

Figure 4: Methods, Tools and Channels of RAISE Strategy

Moreover, a **variety of channels** will be used in order to effectively reach out the identified key audiences, taking into consideration the specific characteristics and needs of each group. The following list is not exhaustive as new needs or opportunities may arise in the course of the project implementation:

- a) **RAISE website**;
- b) **RAISE social media** (*Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn*) and **YouTube channel**;
- c) **Workshops, conferences, datathons, exhibitions and other events**;
- d) **Journals, scientific magazines and conference papers**;
- e) **Communication synergies** (*liaison activities*) with EOSC projects and organisations;
- f) **EOSC forum**;
- g) **Partners' website**, social media and other networks.

Overall, project partners' presentations and participation at third party events (*e.g. conferences, exhibitions, webinars etc.*) in parallel with the organization of **RAISE events** ensure its high visibility to public, engagement with the target audiences and attention attracting to press / media. Together with the scientific publications, the aforementioned activities foster exploitation and uptake of the project results.

Lastly, dissemination synergies with other **EU funded projects**, and particularly with **EOSC projects**, strengthen collaboration with relevant research organizations, business stakeholders from the industry sector and policy makers. Overall, the knowledge exchange with the EOSC community can be facilitated and lessons learned as well as experiences can be shared.

2.3.1 Logo and Visual Identity

The RAISE brand is consisted of the **logo, name, acronym and symbol** that distinguishes it from other projects. For this reason, the first RAISE activity performed in the context of communication and dissemination was its creation.

The **RAISE logo** is consisted of a range of colours that will be cohesive in both print and digital use (*online presence, printed materials, templates, documents etc.*) which assist in creating a strong and

consistence visual presence. The two official brand colours present in the logo are mild pink combined with lively emerald. The colour codes are provided below:

- **Pink**
 RGB 255/92/128
 CMYK 0/76/27/0
 #ff5b7f
- **Green**
 RGB 0/134/145
 CMYK 90/0/33/25
 #00879

Figure 5: RAISE logo

The **visual identity** of the project is consisted of the **tangible and visual elements** which namely are **templates** (*letterhead, PowerPoint, Word, Agenda*), **printed material** (*factsheet, brochure, poster*), **online presence** (*website, social media, e-newsletter*) and **audio-visual materials** (*video / podcasts*). The aforementioned materials will assist to the effective communication of the project to target audience and beyond in all types of activities.

2.3.2 Website

The project’s website is the main **online communication channel** of RAISE with the stakeholders and general public. It serves as a medium for conveying the project’s results to target groups and sustaining them after the end of its lifecycle. The **RAISE website** will include **public deliverables; publications** (*pre-prints or under any other form that could lawfully be available to public, especially in accordance with the RAISE Consortium Agreement obligations of the partners*); **project activities** such as *workshops, datathons, demonstrations, presentations* and so on; **links** from the **established dissemination synergies** with similar EU funded projects as well as news from any performed joint activities with them. When the project nears its completion, the emphasis of website’s content will change from **project oriented** to **results oriented**. For providing to the reader an overview about the website and its content a site map depiction is given in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6: Site Map

VILABS is the responsible partner for the **maintenance** of the website and the **update** of its content will be continuous throughout the project's duration. The **performance** will be monitored in a monthly basis by VILABS via the **Google Analytics tool** and partners will be informed regularly (*or upon request by the project coordinator*).

2.3.3 Social Media

The social media platforms are very powerful online channels for transmitting messages and communicating with target audiences in almost real time. For this reason, the RAISE consortium created the project's accounts on [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#) (*page*) and [Facebook](#) (*page*) since the very beginning (*M1*).

The social media accounts are managed and updated by VILABS while all partners are responsible to provide content that would possibly interest the target groups. Moreover, partners are strongly encouraged to disseminate the project's social media posts via their own online channels. Particularly, the content that will be posted may include (*but not limited to*):

- RAISE **public deliverables**;
- RAISE **press releases**;
- RAISE **e-newsletter issues**;
- RAISE **publications** (*including available links*);
- Participation/presentations in events and conferences;
- **Outreach activities** (*workshops, demonstrations, other events*) organized by the consortium;
- **Liaison activities** (*synergies*) with other EOSC projects and similar EU funded ones;
- **News** from project meetings;
- **Promotional materials**.

The visibility of posts will be enhanced by **hashtags** related to the project's topic so more followers can be attracted. The main hashtag to be used is the **#RaiseScience** for grouping all conversations around the project while the selected hashtags for its promotion follow:

- #OpenScience
- #OpenAccess
- #OpenData
- #EOSC
- #HorizonEurope
- #FAIRprinciples
- #DataSharing
- #OpenResearchData
- #HorizonEU
- #EUresearch
- #EU_Project
- **Official hashtags** of public events where consortium partners have presented the project and / or participated as exhibitors with RAISE booths.
- **Hashtags of cities and countries** where the RAISE pilot activities, workshops, conference and overall outreach events take place.

Within the same context the official tags of the project, **@RaiseScience** on Twitter, **@RAISE Science** on LinkedIn, and **@RAISE science** on Facebook will be employed. Other tags that can be inserted at the social media posts of the project are:

- **EOSC Association** (*@eoscassociation*) that actively supports RAISE.
- **Project partners' official social media accounts** (*organizational*);
- **Project partners' personal accounts** (*names*) - if available - for giving credits as a recognition of his/her work and/or achievements within the project activities e.g. tagging the authors of a RAISE scientific publication.

- End-users' organisation.
- Events that RAISE partners participate
- VIPs that actively support the project through their participation in outreach events of RAISE and / or any other action that express support to the project.
- Other **similar EU funded projects** that RAISE has established communication synergies (*liaison activities*).
- The official tag of the **Horizon Europe** for **RAISE Twitter account** the tag **@HorizonEU** and for the **RAISE LinkedIn Page** the tag **@HORIZON_EU**

The **RAISE consortium** for ensuring the effective social media coverage of its outreach events will follow the guidelines of the H2020 programme entitled [Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects](#)¹ which are:

- **At least 6 weeks in advance:** The hashtags that will be used are decided. First posts about the event should be made and shared amongst the RAISE network.
- **At least 1 month in advance:** Web content will be created and be promoted via RAISE start promoting it social media account using the event hashtag. Moreover, an event image should be prepared for sharing it on tweets and LinkedIn posts.
- **Several days before the event:** A list of event speakers and participants will be prepared with relevant Twitter handles to engage with before and during the event. Also, a list of posts to tweet during the event will be created. Scheduled posts (*if possible*) can also be considered in order to focus on live discussions during the event.
- **During the event:** Tweets in real time (*live –tweet*) with interesting pictures (*or screenshots in virtual events*); tags and mentions partners, organizations and speakers; dedicated hashtag of the event should be further promoted. Lastly, it is recommended that participants to be asked to join the conversation. When needed related content, scientific studies, published papers, web content can be included in live posts.
- **After the event:** During the days following the event, the results of the social media activities will be monitored and information relevant of the event can be kept posting that include the event's hashtag.

2.3.4 E-newsletter

The project's **newsletter issues** will be sent via email to all subscribers announcing news and developments in an easy-to-read manner addressed to all target groups. Links from the RAISE website will be mainly used (*reciprocal links*) without though excluding external ones when referred to project's scientific publications or other significant links that prove high visibility of the project in press and media. Within the project's website a subscription box is available where anyone interested in learning about the latest updates of RAISE can **voluntarily register** and then receive the project's newsletter issues. It should be stressed that all collected data from the subscription process is treated according to **GDPR**².

The e-newsletters issues will be published when the consortium has major announcements to make and communicate with its stakeholders/subscribers. However, an estimation based to the overall project's planning anticipates at least **6 issues** in total while more details about the execution time are provided in **chapter 3** within the action plan (*calendar*). VILABS will lead this activity while all partners will be required to contribute with content from their work made in the RAISE project, photos (*if available*), links and any other information and/or activity that could be publicized. Prior publishing any newsletter issue at least **a week before** the consortium will receive the final version of each issue for reviewing it.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/eu-data-protection-rules_en

2.3.5 Press Releases

Press releases will be distributed to **national** and **European mass media** as formal announcements of project's developments. All press releases will be published in **English** and, if necessary, they will be translated in partner's language (upon their responsibility) for achieving the maximum visibility. VILABS will draft the content of the press releases and partners will be asked to contribute with further information if necessary. It is important to be mentioned that all press releases shall have the approval of the consortium.

2.3.6 Promotional Materials

The **RAISE promotional materials** will be produced for supporting the communication and dissemination actions during face-to-face or web-based ones. They will be available for distribution in all kind of events and meetings with stakeholders and will be printed upon the consortium needs.

The materials should follow the visual identity of the project and necessarily include the following information: *RAISE logo; RAISE title and acronym; project's website (URL), contact details of the consortium; EOSC logo; the EU emblem and the required acknowledgement text; disclaimer for excluding REA's responsibility, RAISE social media accounts; a QR code which is linked with the project's website; and logos of project partners.*

All produced promotional materials will be available in digital format at project's website.

2.3.7 YouTube Channel and RAISE videos

YouTube is an online video sharing platform which is also considered as a social media platform. It is very famous worldwide and large audience can be reached. The project will create its own YouTube channel for sharing the RAISE videos. The production of **three RAISE videos** is foreseen for project's promotion (*in Y1*) and presentation of its developments and results (*in Y2 and Y3*).

2.3.8 Scientific Publications

The RAISE scientific papers and technical articles will be submitted for publication in conference proceedings and scientific peer-reviewed journals in Europe and beyond. Specifically, conference proceeding papers are an effective way to present new ideas, introduce work performed within the project to colleagues, and optimize research questions. Moreover, project's publications will assist in promoting possible follow-up of research activities. Overall, the route of **Open Access** in trustworthy repositories for RAISE publications will be pursued provided that all obligations to **protect results, confidentiality obligations** and obligations to protect **personal data** will be met.

Lastly, the [Open Research Europe platform](#) supported by EC will also be considered as possible / alternative route for publishing RAISE results.

2.3.9 Organization of RAISE Outreach Events

The outreach events of the project will ensure target audience's engagement with the aim to receive their feedback. For this reason, the organization of a series of RAISE events is foreseen and listed:

- **2 workshops** under the auspices of major events bringing together relevant stakeholders and involving them in collaborative research activities, trainings, consultations, etc.
- **One high profile final conference** with relevant stakeholder representatives, in order to disseminate the major outcomes of the project.
- **three large datathons** will be organised (*one every project year*).

During the datathons events that will last from several hours to days researchers will carry out research using the datasets made available in the pilot RAI Certified Nodes. Scientific community will be made aware of these events on the engagement with user communities. The researchers that will win in the competition part of the events, will be encouraged to disseminate the RAI concept by continuing the research and preparing joint publications with the RAISE consortium, producing RAI identifiers within the publication.

Lastly, other events to be organized by the consortium are **capacity building activities** and **training** of new researchers on the RAISE solution usage. The targeted audience will be both new researchers that wish to learn about RAISE solution and research entities that wish to harmonise their dataset and provide privacy-preserving experiment processing services with the developed standards. To achieve these aims **summer schools**, **webinars** and a **training programme** as well as **fast track training** for researchers joining the calls for **external researchers** will be organized.

2.3.10 Participation in Third Party Events

A significant dissemination method is the consortium's participation in **third party events** such as workshops, conferences, exhibitions, forums, symposiums and other types of events (*e.g. fairs*). The RAISE presence in such events will be targeted primarily in informing end-users as well as EOSC community. Through participation of the RAISE consortium in such events the project will be widely introduced to target audiences and assist in knowledge exchange process. A detailed list of events has been build up and is available in **Annex II** of this deliverable.

2.3.11 EOSC FORUM Platform

EOSC FORUM platform is the EOSC-Association community platform that enables its members a more efficient and interactive tool for joint activities, exchange of information and networking. To this end, the RAISE project will utilize this platform so as to inform and reach the EOSC community for its developments and results and interact with its members.

2.3.12 Synergies with other EU funded projects

Effective networking is about building strong relationships and liaisons over time that can lead to mutual understanding and trust that would benefit all involved parties. Such liaisons (*synergies*) that would expand the project's network and promote the knowledge exchange will be sought with EOSC projects and, also, ones with similar topic to RAISE. This practice will help the consortium's effort to raise the project's positive reputation and take-up its solution in the long term.

2.3.13 Partners' Communication Channels and Networks

The **RAISE consortium** consists of prestigious organisations with longstanding experience related to the project's topic and has a **strong network** and **contacts** amongst the target audience in pan-European level and beyond. Furthermore, it holds communication channels (*websites, social media accounts etc.*) of high visibility and traffic from stakeholders. Thus, partners' communication channels and networks will be utilized for promoting RAISE and assist in creating the initial community interested to learn about its produced results.

The support to the dissemination activities of RAISE will further **expand the project's network** and, also, through the **word-of-mouth** positive reputation will be built (*Snowball effect*). Later, at a more mature phase of the project **when results are available**, partners will reveal them via their own channels and networks. Lastly, **after the completion of RAISE**, partners will sustain the project's results and will keep on communicating them when they deem appropriate (*in terms of time, channels and network*) in respect to intellectual property rights and confidentiality of results.

For reader's ease, a summary of the available communications channels and networks is provided below along with a diagram (see **Figure 7**) for representation of the extracted results by the Questionnaire (see **1.3.3 section**) while the detailed list is enclosed in **Annex 1**. In sum,

- **Eighteen (18) official websites** of partners' organization, can feature RAISE project developments mainly at their news sections;
- At least **twenty-three (23) official social media accounts** of project partners can share RAISE developments and results;
- **Seven (7) project partners** that periodically distribute (**online**) **newsletters** to their network can feature the project and its results;
- **Five (5) project partners** are able to publish **press releases** for communicating the RAISE developments;

- **Six (6) project partners** can share via their YouTube channels videos produced by RAISE;
- **Five (5) project partners** can mention and share information about RAISE at their **organization’s promotional material**;
- Contacts in **six (6) Ministries, Municipalities and policy makers** (*in general*) have been identified and can be mobilized by RAISE partners for dissemination activities.
- **Two (2) Mass Media** have been named by project partners and can be contacted when needed for wide communication of RAISE to the general public.
- **Two (2) contact points** (*organizations*) have been identified by RAISE and through them the industry community can be **reached out**.
- **Six (6) Universities and Research centres** have been listed as a strong network of project partners that can be utilized for conveying the produced results of RAISE.
- **Two (2) Open Data Repositories and National Data Services** can be used through RAISE partners’ network for reaching out thousands content providers, included, data repositories and national data services.
- **Seventeen (17) other EU funded projects** with some relation to the RAISE topic can be reached for cross communication activities as project partners have strong collaboration with them (mainly as partners).

Figure 7: Partners’ Communication Channels and Networks

2.4 Dissemination Content and Key Messages

2.4.1 Dissemination Content

Dissemination activities ensure that the project results are conveyed to the scientific community, policy makers and industry while using scientific language prioritizing accuracy. Overall, the project’s results consist of any tangible or intangible output generated by the action, such as data, knowledge and information as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights. They can be used either by the project partners or other relevant stakeholders outside the project for commercial exploitation (*e.g., concrete products or services*) and / or lay the foundation for further research work (*e.g., novel knowledge, insights, technologies, methods, data*).

For this reason, the dissemination actions are crucial for maximising the potential impact of RAISE results. The consortium for ensuring the success of this goal has detailed the content that shall be used and include information about:

- **Knowledge, data, methods, best practices** and so on produced by the **RAISE project** during its lifecycle which might be useful to stakeholders for further exploitation. It should be stressed that the related intellectual property rights of RAISE project partners shall be ensured **a priori**.
- **RAISE Scientific publications** (*available links to be included*) or part of them along with the proper citation.
- **Partners' presentations** (*PowerPoint presentation files*) in conferences and events without disclosing confidential information.
- **Partners' participation** in conferences, EOSC events / meetings, fairs and third party events in general accompanied with short description of the activities performed.
- **Events organized by RAISE consortium** along with a description of the activity, lessons learnt and related results produced.
- **Synergies established** with EOSC projects and other **EU funded ones** (*available links to be included*) with main focus on the knowledge exchange occurred.
- **Promotional material** (*digital or printed*) such as flyers, posters, banners of RAISE events (*in digital format*) which include description of the project, its objectives and expected results.
- References (*or interviews*) in **mass media** which present the findings of RAISE project.
- RAISE **public deliverables** or part of them accompanied by the proper citation of the document.
- **Blog posts** written by project partners describing their **work made within RAISE** and their findings to be published on RAISE website.
- RAISE **press releases** where major developments of the project are announced.

2.4.2 Key Messages

The **key messages** selected per audience for disseminating the project are enclosed in **table 4**.

Audience	Key Messages
<p>Researchers (<i>data providers & data processors</i>)</p>	<p>Long Message (<i>descriptive</i>):</p> <p>RAISE project facilitates the data availability for researchers, by adopting a reproducible workflow that publishes the code and data in a form that allows other researchers to extend the approach to new applications with a minimum of effort.</p> <p>Short Messages (<i>catchword / slogan</i>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimise your analysis time and protect your data while applying best practices for Open Science and FAIR data management” • Scripts for processing open data can be easily assessed in terms of maintainability and software quality • Researchers, send your code to the data and not your data to the compute centres! Open your data for others to process them and get cited! • RAISE helps you to analyse data without actually accessing them • Openness in science and data, share methods and data • Top Quality and Credible Data Analysis Software • Open Science for researchers!
<p>Publishers & Open Data Repositories</p>	<p>Long Message (<i>descriptive</i>):</p> <p>RAISE offers a solution that enables the research community to publish their outcomes with evidence-based authenticity of the data-analysis.</p>

	<p>Short Messages (<i>catchword / slogan</i>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pipelines offering the ability to execute published scripts on known datasets can be a valuable tool for validating/replicating published studies • Provide researchers accreditation of their data and analysis • Enabling the early sharing of data analysis • Make friendly user interface for the repositories • Open data sharing and processing
<p>EOSC Community</p>	<p>Long Message (<i>descriptive</i>):</p> <p>RAISE project provides the effective tools that comply with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, in order to enhance the Open Science ecosystem and EOSC with services that enable FAIRness of data.</p> <p>Short Messages (<i>catchword / slogan</i>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing the EOSC with data analysis PIDs • Creating an Open Science trusted space for the analysis of data • Decentralized open science • Further disseminate the importance of open data • Send your code to the data and not your data to the compute centres! • Open your data for others to process them and get cited!
<p>Industry (<i>companies with algorithms</i>) & Potential Investors</p>	<p>Long Message (<i>descriptive</i>):</p> <p>RAISE project develops innovative services that provide the mechanisms and long-term resources for seamless access, discovery, analysis and on-demand provisioning of open science data and tools and will comply with the EOSC Rules of Participation to be integrated with and offered through the EOSC.</p> <p>Short Messages (<i>catchword / slogan</i>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test your algorithms in various datasets without worrying about ethics and data protection • Share data with scientist and regulatory authorities / needs for transparency • Trusted decentralized sharing of open data • Making Open Science data exploitable
<p>General Public</p>	<p>Long Message (<i>descriptive</i>):</p> <p>RAISE offers a solution that enables the research community to publish their outcomes with evidence-based authenticity of the data-analysis.</p> <p>Short Messages (<i>catchword / slogan</i>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RAISE enables data analysis without data sharing • Open data processing and sharing

- Science is evolving to open forms
- Building trust in data

Table 4: Dissemination Key Messages

2.5 Rules, Procedures and Obligations

According to the contractual obligations of the consortium, partners are required to follow certain acknowledgement rules when publicising work related to RAISE results. In addition, procedures have been set prior the performance of dissemination actions by the project partners. The following sub-sections provide a detailed explication.

2.5.1 Dissemination Obligations and Rules

Topic	Rules
Publications	<p>The following acknowledgement text should be included in all publications related to the RAISE work:</p> <p><i>“ This work is a part of the RAISE project (grant agreement No 101058479) funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”</i></p>
Open science: <i>open access to scientific publications</i>	<p>The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications - immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.
Disclaimer <i>(for all communication & dissemination activities)</i>	<p>According to Article 17.3 of the Grant Agreement, any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (<i>translated into local languages where appropriate</i>):</p> <p><i>“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”</i></p>
EU emblem	<p>Communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (<i>including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.</i>), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (<i>emblem</i>) and funding statement (<i>translated into local languages, where</i></p>

	<p><i>appropriate</i>). The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.</p> <p>Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (<i>e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors</i>), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos. For the purposes of their obligations under Article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.</p>
Mass Media	<p>Before engaging in a communication activity expected to have a major media impact the consortium has to inform the Research Executive Agency.</p>

Table 5: Dissemination Obligations and Rules

2.5.2 Dissemination Procedures

The consortium before realizing any dissemination activity shall follow the dissemination procedures as foreseen in **Article 17 (Annex I)** of the Grant Agreement which include **guidelines** and **define the main steps** to be taken. Thus, project partners are requested to follow the procedures before any publication and / or presentation of results related to the work performed within **RAISE project**. The main reasons for setting the dissemination procedures in RAISE are to:

- Ensure **high quality** of **RAISE publications** and **presentations**;
- Avoid overlaps**;
- Avoid disclosure** of **project's confidential** information;
- Ensure IP protection of all partners** (*background & foreground*)
- Monitor** and **record** the **dissemination activities** of the project.

Step No.	Requested Actions to be performed by partners
Step 1	<p>15 days before the performance of any publication / presentation of results related to the RAISE project, the initiator of the dissemination activity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fills in the dissemination request form (<i>see Annex III</i>) providing necessary information (<i>type of activity, provisional title, short summary or draft of the whole paper/set of slides, if available</i>); Informs via email the WP6 Leader (VILABS) <p>As soon as available, the initiator shares the abstract / draft paper/draft poster, etc., in a dedicated folder on the project online collaboration tool i.e. teams (<i>creating a corresponding folder for the related event</i>), and informs VILABS when it is done.</p>
Step 2	<p>The WP6 Leader (VILABS) sends via email the request within 2 days to the Consortium partners - <i>in copy (cc) the Project Coordinator (AUTH)</i> - for approval, modification, request for extra information/clarifications, or rejection.</p>
Step 3	<p>The Consortium partners have to reply to the WP6 Leader within 5 days in case of rejection, clarification needed or any other objection that may arise; <u>no response is considered as an approval</u>;</p>
Step 4	<p>The WP6 Leader (VILABS) informs the initiator. In case of:</p>

	<p>a. Approval (or no response received): The initiator may proceed with the submission or realization of the planned action;</p> <p>b. Conflict / objection: Any consortium member and / or Project Coordinator, can object to the proposed dissemination activity, for example in cases of overlaps or risk of disclosure of confidential information. <u>The objection has to include a clear reasoning as well as a precise request for necessary modifications.</u></p> <p>The issue is discussed among the Coordinator, the WP6 Leader and the involved partners.</p>
Step 5	<p>Within 10 working days after the realization of the approved dissemination activity, the initiator of the dissemination activity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uploads the final paper, presentation, poster, or other presented material on the project online collaboration tool i.e. teams, in the dedicated folder; • Uploads photos from the activity, if relevant, in the same folder (<i>in a “photos” sub-folder</i>); • Completes a dissemination-activities report template (see Annex IV) and uploads it in the same folder; • Informs via email the WP6 Leader (VILABS); <p>The WP6 Leader (VILABS) records all dissemination activities performed in the project, for progress reporting purposes, as well as publication on the website of the related presentation, poster and / or paper (<i>if available in public</i>).</p>

Table 6: Dissemination Procedures (step-by-step)

It should be stressed that if partners wish to present or release material already approved, then no formal approval is required, but the WP6 leader (VILABS) has to be informed.

2.6 Metrics and Targets

The consortium has set targets for the performance of project’s communication activities since the proposal phase and they are provided in the table that follow. The performed activities will be regularly measured and monitored for their success in accordance with the related indicators.

Type of activity	Metrics description	Target per Year		
		Y1	Y2	Y3
Production of Promotional Material	Design and production of information brochures, posters and factsheets	At least 1 brochure and 1 poster developed in <u>partner’s languages</u> plus English	Update of the materials according to the progress of the project focusing on results and generated impact	Update of the materials according to the progress of the project focusing on results and generated impact
Create Project’s Website online identity	Project Website	250 visits / per month	500 visits / per month	750+ visits / per month
	Project Blog posts	1 blog post / per month	At least 2 blog posts / per month	At least 2 blog posts / per month

Social Media	Posts	At least 1 post / week	At least 2 posts / week	At least 2 posts / week
	RAISE Twitter Account	500 followers (in total)	700 followers (in total)	1.000 followers (in total)
	RAISE LinkedIn Page	100 connections (in total)	300 connections (in total)	500 followers (in total)
	RAISE Facebook Account	300 likes (in total)	500 likes (in total)	700 likes (in total)
YouTube <i>(videos etc.)</i>	Video creation	1 video will be developed for project visual presentation and promotion.	A second video will present the product/service	A third video include information on the project pilots, the impact generated & the sustainability potential
	Views	300 views / per YouTube video	300 views / per YouTube video	300 views / per YouTube video
Synergies / Clustering	Cluster with other similar HE project	At least 1 project	At least 2 projects	At least 3 projects
Generating positive media coverage: <i>Articles, interviews, Press releases, Newsletters</i>	Articles	At least 30 Articles by the end of the project		
	Interviews	At least 15 interviews by the end of the project		
	Press Releases	At least 12 press releases by the end of the project		
	e-Newsletters	At least 6 newsletter issues by the end of the project		
Networking Activities	Participation in conferences, workshops, trade fairs, Exhibitions Horizon Europe and other EC events	At least 30 such activities during the project's lifecycle		
Project Events Organization	Workshops	at least 2 workshops under the auspices of major events bringing together relevant stakeholders and involving them in collaborative research activities, trainings, consultations, etc.		
	Final Conference	One (1) high profile final conference will be organized with relevant stakeholder representatives, in order to disseminate the major outcomes of the project.		
	Attendees	At least 100 attendees in each event		
	Follow up activities	At least 30 Number of Follow-up activities per event		
Open Access publications / policy briefs	Popularized publications	At least 4 popularised publications		
	Policy briefs	At least 2 policy briefs		
	Scientific publications	At least 10 scientific publications		

Table 7: Metris and Targets

3 Communication and Dissemination Plan

The communication and dissemination plan is divided in two parts, the **Calendar of Dissemination Activities** (see 3.1 section) and the **Action Plan** (see 3.2 section). The first part is a timeline of actions that stem from the GA while the second one lists the partners' intentions for disseminating RAISE through various channels.

3.1 Calendar of Communication and Dissemination Activities

The **calendar** includes the **planned activities** under chronological order (*quarterly*) as well as the ones that have already been performed till the submission of the current deliverable. By **M6** (March 2023) the consortium had already created the **visual identity** of the project and prepared its **official templates**, produced (*in digital format*), set up the project's **social media**, launched the project's **website**, published its **1st press release** and collected partners' **individual communication and dissemination plans**.

Project Month	Actual Month	Quarters	Activity	Lead partner / contributor
M1	October 2022	Q1	Visual identity creation (project logo, official templates)	VILABS
M2	November 2022		Social Media set up	VILABS
M3	December 2022		Website launch	VILABS
M3	December 2022		1 st Press Release published	VILABS
M4	January 2023	Q2	WP6 Questionnaire creation	VILABS
M5	February 2023		Collection of partners individual communication and dissemination plans	VILABS
M6	March 2023		Finalization of D6.1	VILABS
M7	April 2023	Q3	Workshop in Kozani	UOWM / all partners
M8	May 2023		Brochure, Factsheet (EN)	VILABS
M9	June 2023		Poster Creation (EN)	VILABS
			4 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners
			2 Blog Post - news items / month	VILABS / all partners

M10	<i>July 2023</i>	Q4	1st Newsletter Issue	VILABS / all partners
M11	<i>August 2023</i>		Promotional Material translation in partners language	All partners
M12	<i>September 2023</i>		1st Video produced for project's promotion	VILABS/ all partners
			Cluster with other similar HE projects	VILABS
			4 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners
			2 Blog Post - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
M13	<i>October 2023</i>	Q5	8 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners
M14	<i>November 2023</i>		2 Blog Post - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
M15	<i>December 2023</i>		Cluster with other similar HE projects	VILABS
M16	<i>January 2024</i>	Q6	8 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners
M17	<i>February 2024</i>		2nd Newsletter Issue	VILABS / all partners
M18	<i>March 2024</i>		2 Blog Posts - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
			Promotional Material Update (Y2)	VILABS / all partners
M19	<i>April 2024</i>	Q7	1st Datathon	VILABS/ WP2, WP5 partners
			8 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners
M20	<i>May 2024</i>		Cluster with other similar HE projects	VILABS
			2 Blog Posts - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
M21	<i>June 2024</i>	1st Summer School	ATHENA	

			Press Release about 1st Summer School results	ATHENA / VILABS
M22	<i>July 2024</i>	Q8	3rd Newsletter Issue	VILABS / all partners
M23	<i>August 2024</i>		Press Release about 1 st Datathon and its results	WP2, WP5 partners / VILABS
			2 Blog Post - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
M24	<i>September 2024</i>		8 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners
			2nd Video produced to present the product/service	VILABS/ all partners
M25	<i>October 2024</i>	Q9	Cluster with other similar HE projects	VILABS
			2 Blog Posts - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
M26	<i>November 2024</i>		2nd Datathon	VILABS / WP2, WP5 partners
			Press Release about 2nd Datathon	WP2, WP5 partners / VILABS
M27	<i>December 2024</i>		8 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners
M28	<i>January 2025</i>	Q10	4th Newsletter Issue	VILABS/ all partners
M29	<i>February 2025</i>		Cluster with other similar HE projects	VILABS
			Promotional Material Update (Y3)	VILABS / all partners
M30	<i>March 2025</i>		8 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners
			2 Blog Posts - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
M31	<i>April 2025</i>	Q11	8 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners

M32	May 2025		3rd Datathon	VILABS WP2, WP5 partners
			2 Blog Posts - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
M33	June 2025		5th Newsletter Issue	VILABS/ all partners
			2nd Summer School	ATHENA
M34	July 2025		8 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners
			Press Release about 2 nd Datathon and its results	WP2, WP5 partners / VILABS
M35	August 2025	Q12	2 Blog Posts - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
			Press Release about 2 nd Summer School and its results	ATHENA / VILABS
M36	September 2025		Cluster with other similar HE projects	VILABS
M37	October 2025		2 Blog Posts - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
			8 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners
M38	November 2025	Q13	3rd video produced that includes information on the project pilots, the impact generated & the sustainability potential	VILABS/ all partners
M39	December 2025		Final Conference	AUTH / all partners
M40	January 2026	Q14 (1/3)	Press Release for announcing the project's closure	VILABS
			6th Newsletter Issue	VILABS
			2 Blog Posts - news items / month	VILABS / all partners
			8 social media posts / month	VILABS / all partners

Table 8: Calendar of C. & D. Activities

3.2 Action Plan

The consortium team, led by WP6 leader (VILABS), created a “log” of activities which include potential participation in third party events, publications and organization of RAISE events. By this list, the RAISE partners mapped the dissemination opportunities related to the project and expressed their plans, intentions, ideas and thoughts that cover its lifecycle. It will serve as a **reference point** to all dissemination activities for combining partner’s resources in a more effective manner that would increase the impact of RAISE; **serve as a catalogue** of third party events for selecting the proper ones in regards the project needs per its implementation phase; provide information about **partners’ thoughts/plans for scientific publications** and **easier identification of co-authors** amongst the consortium, establish a **common understanding** about the RAISE events to be organized and contribute if possible; assist WP6 leader in **identifying dissemination opportunities**, coordinate partners efficiently, provide them support where necessary and **monitor** the actions for reporting purposes in a more structured pattern; and lastly provide to the project coordinator an **overview of consortium’s intentions** and if needed support partners / propose corrective actions as well as alternatives after a thorough discussion with them.

For reader’s ease, a summary of the **Action Plan** is provided below along with a diagram (*Figure 8*) which represents the findings by WP6 Questionnaire (*see 1.3.3 section*). A detailed list is enclosed in **Annex II** which can be considered as a tentative Action Plan and **in no case** as a report of performed actions **neither** as a commitment where non-implementation of some actions mentioned herein brings any kind of consequences. The only legal document that defines consequences in the case of non-compliance with the agreed activities is the Grant Agreement. In sum,

- **Sixty-eight (68) third party events** (*in total*) have been identified and listed by the consortium which include conferences, EOSC events and meetings, forums, symposium, fairs and so on where RAISE project can be communicated via face-to-face activities, presentations, papers, posters and booths/stands. Partners that have expressed their intentions, plans and thoughts to participate or attend those events can be found in column “*Involved Partner/s*” (*see Annex II*).
- At least **six (6) RAISE events** (*physical and virtual*) open to stakeholders for engaging them, promoting the project, its objectives as well as the available results;
- **Sixteen (16) scientific publication routes** have been identified at this early stage of the project with potential topics proposed in some cases for further reflection and collaboration amongst the consortium.

Figure 8: Depiction of RAISE tentative Action Plan

4 Exploitation Plan

The communication and dissemination activities that the consortium plans to perform such as scientific publications, participation to third party events, stakeholders' engagement via project's events and so on will **pave the way** for the exploitation of RAISE solution. Complementary, the exploitation plan will direct partners' related efforts for defining RAISE solution's end users (*"consumers" of RAISE services*) and potential investors (*"buyers" of RAISE services*); determine their needs and meet them where possible via targeted services; specify the RAISE results and examine potential market uptake; define the foreground knowledge produced and protect the intellectual property of RAISE partners (*individually and as a whole*); update partner's individual plans related to the results produced within the project and owned by them; and overall ensure the **sustainability** of the RAISE solution in long term (*beyond the completion of the EU funding*).

4.1 Exploitation Objectives

The RAISE consortium has specified **the main axes** where will focus its exploitation efforts, the **partners** that shall be **involved in** as well as the **desired outcome**. It should be noted that all efforts and actions to be made will be complementary to each. The table below outlines the objectives, the goals and the measures to be taken.

Exploitation Focus	Type	Strategic Goals	Measures to be taken
Integration and uptake within EOSC	Joint (<i>all partners</i>)	RAISE outputs onboarding in EOSC portal and community uptake	Liaisons with EOSC Association and their members to promote the RAISE "game changing" concepts (Open Science/FAIR)
Joint exploitation of RAISE components (<i>big data management, AI analytics, and the user centric interfaces</i>)	Joint	Establishing a viable route to market for RAISE solutions with the participation of all partners.	Links with GAIA-X and its community for elaboration of needs. Business plan elaboration. Preparation of Joint Exploitation path
Strengthening partners' existing individual activities	Individual Exploitation Plans	Enhancing partners' existing products / services with project outcomes.	Each partner will elaborate on their initial exploitation plan in-line with its research and business strategies
Sustaining the pilot cases and expanding to other thematic communities	Pilot Partners	Expanding and exploiting the pilot outcomes	- Exploitation case elaboration for specific pilot outcomes -Further research and commercial aspects elaborated in a roadmap

Table 9: Exploitation Objectives

4.2 End Users and Investors Mapping

The overall framework of the exploitation actions aim to put in use the produced results of the RAISE project. For this reason, it is important to establish within the consortium a common understanding about the categories which comprise the end users of the RAISE solution and perceive the kind of potential investors. Towards this goal, a preliminary discussion was conducted and via the **WP6**

Questionnaire RAISE partners provided their views on the topic. The collected input was categorized as follows:

- **End users:** *research institutes; universities and postgraduate students / PhD students; researchers; governmental agencies e.g., on transport, renewable energy sources; some of the OpenAIRE NOADs (in 37 countries in EU and EEA) could find it useful to add RAISE in their institutional catalogues; publishers of scientific journals/conferences; clinicians; university hospitals that are in need to process large scale data for epidemic research; city municipalities, regulatory authorities; hospitals; Researchers are broadly potential end users.*
- **Investors:** *pharmaceutical companies; companies of cloud and data infrastructures; big data companies; EU grants for applying further research; Health providers; all National Open Science Cloud Initiatives (NOSCI) are potential users and investors.*

It should be noted that partners have also named some potential investors and end users, however this information is not revealed and remains confidential within the consortium as the dissemination level of the current deliverable is public.

4.3 SWOT Analysis

A **S.W.O.T. analysis** is a method used for identifying the **strengths** and **weaknesses** that an organization has in its **internal environment** and in parallel understanding the **opportunities** and **threats** that occur at its **external environment**. It should be mentioned that strengths and opportunities are considered as **helpful** segments while weaknesses and threats as **harmful** ones. Within this context, an evaluation of RAISE current status is made and comprehension of the efforts along with the improvements to be made is achieved.

The consortium conducted its own **S.W.O.T. analysis** for assessing the aforementioned aspects which assisted it in defining the upcoming exploitation efforts more effectively. In **Table 10**, the collected information via WP6 Questionnaire is presented in detail.

Particularly, project partners were requested to provide their view by answering related questions to strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats around RAISE. The questions were divided to the respected categories and are provided below.

- **(S) trengths:** Taking into consideration the overall RAISE solution - What are the elements that are addressing the end user needs? Which are the innovative capabilities of RAISE that can stand out?
- **(W) eaknesses:** What do we have in shortage and what can be improved?
- **(O) pportunities:** What do the targeted End Users need for executing their day-to-day work more effectively? Focusing on RAISE solution, what knowledge, tools, and resources do we need to develop/acquire for satisfying the End User’s needs?
- **(T) hreats:** Can you foresee any challenges / obstacles for the RAISE solution? Are there any competitive novel solutions that can potentially be preferred by End Users for satisfying their needs?

Questions	RAISE partners’ input
<p>Strengths</p> <p><i>Taking into consideration the overall RAISE solution - What are the elements that are addressing the end user needs? Which are the innovative</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy discovery and exploitation of data sets • Effective dissemination of data sets and scientific results • Increased security and control of data / operational environment • Easy execution and replication of experiments • One stop shop solution for all the needs of end researchers • Crowdsourcing of resources, keeping the data within your premises, accreditation for data ownership

<p>capabilities of RAISE that can stand out?</p> <p>#Tags: Internal Environment; Helpful</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bringing researchers into EOSC. So far the researcher’s perspective has not been successfully into EOSC as RAISE project plans to do, especially in the design phase of services as most EOSC onboarded services already existed. • For researchers the effortless replication/validation of existing studies innovative feature: the ability to execute algorithms without downloading the dataset. • Decentralized architecture Algorithm comes to data interdisciplinary approach. • Effort to show how different data type and ontologies can contribute to solutions to real society problems. • Holistic approach of patient condition as well as holistic research strategy when it comes to data targeting same research domains. • The users who are sceptic in opening their data, may allow other users to crunch their own data if they know that the users that will be using their data will be tracked, that they will be cited for the publication or other results achieved. The ability to reuse, process and analyse data remotely and collaborate with others, possibly also co-publishing results. • Shared Data Shared Software Top Quality Data and Software
<p>Weaknesses</p> <p><i>What do we have in shortage and what can be improved?</i></p> <p>#Tags: Internal Environment; Harmful</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to increase popularity among researchers and policy stakeholders. • Gain the trust of end users and organizations. • Avoid complexities and high obstacles. • Hide underline functionalities and provide clear / effective tools. • Data privacy issues, how will we make sure that the whole dataset is not shared and that the results downloaded are anonymous. • Utilising existing solutions, e.g., OpenAIRE dashboard, to enable interconnections with the EOSC Graph. • Security and trust Geographical / Country constraints • Processing data might take time and it should be considered early in the project. • The weak points of RAISE are bound with the fact that repositories may not allow remote code to be processed. And, thus, the expansion of the RAISE system beyond the RAISE nodes may be difficult. Also, the ones coming from the security threats.
<p>Opportunities</p> <p><i>What do the targeted End Users need for executing their day-to-day work more effectively? Focusing on RAISE solution, what knowledge, tools, and resources do we need to develop/acquire for</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of a central hub for all operations • Easy cataloguing of datasets and results • Integrated set of tools with secure access and increased availability • Intuitive user interfaces, easy process, quick analysis (computer power) and modules that increase productivity. • User friendly interfaces for non-expert users • Increased extensibility and replication • Low cost of maintenance and use • Data, Processing / Computing resources, Provenance Reproducibility open research data management

<p>satisfying the End Users' needs?</p> <p>#Tags: External Environment; Helpful</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on what matters most when we communicate RAISE to researchers, i.e., what it can do to support their research questions and not the FAIR principles. We have the opportunity to make a powerful infrastructure with high uptake and impact if we focus on what researchers actually need. • Better understanding of clinical and / or clinical research conditions based on the available tools from RAISE solution. Promote the open data/open research to European level and show the potential for clinical research and for healthcare systems across Europe. • Opportunities for opening and sharing data, opportunities for collaboration, opportunities for reproducible science, opportunities for citation of data and linkage with publications.
<p>Threats</p> <p>Can you foresee any challenges / obstacles for the RAISE solution? Are there any competitive novel solutions that can potentially be preferred by End Users for satisfying their needs?</p> <p>#Tags: External Environment; Harmful</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased complexities may hinder implementation. • Low usability may frustrate end users. • Penetration among researchers may not be efficient. • Increased maintenance costs • The cross analysis among RAI nodes is an important use-case that cannot be satisfied. This might discourage end users. • The project will also develop things that already exist, such as a repository and a pre-print server (also a PID for RAISE data, check https://www.raid.org.au/), while EOSC is all about not re-inventing the wheel, but collaborating and interconnecting with existing services. • Little adoption multiple site orchestrated analysis workflows • GDPR is contradictory to open data. • Cybersecurity threats that actively targeting this kind of critical infrastructures. We should include a role in our project for cybersecurity monitoring. • Security (allowing remote code to run in its systems) is probably the main threat for the project. If not properly secured, the RAISE system can open doors for exploitation of systems.

Table 10: SWOT Analysis of RAISE

This analysis will be periodically discussed throughout the project's duration and modifications / updates will be applied where and when necessary, upon RAISE's developments.

4.4 Expected Impact

The research and innovation breakthroughs of **RAISE solution** will provide a **competitive advantage** not only to its partners but also to **wider research** and **scientific community** and **academia**, and **business**, that will be able to exploit the various project outputs. Such advantages have been identified since the proposal phase of the project and are listed per category at the table that follows.

Categories of Key Stakeholders	Expected Impact
<p>Researchers - data providers (including RIs, clusters, long tail of science)</p>	<p>RAISE will enhance productivity by simplifying the workflow, accreditation of their contribution, data plagiarism for originality and ownership, simplifying data anonymization and privacy measures, raw data can be transformed to reusable with the minimum effort and the higher security</p>

	required, even small-scale contributions (small size datasets) can be jointly processed for generalizing research findings
Researchers - data processors	RAISE will enhance productivity by simplifying the workflow, - it will allow researchers to spend more time focusing on the interpretation of the analysis and the quality of results rather than the technical issues, - it will foster interdisciplinary cooperation through enhancing accessible data and methodologies, available processing resources from the community, tools for replicability and reproducibility, less bandwidth required for accessing big datasets, tools for automating continuous analysis of distributed datasets, data becomes not only as open as possible but also as open as needed
Industry <i>(companies with algorithms)</i>	- Scientific output will flow from the theoretical research to market practice, thus creating more effective, competitive and focused on the needs of the customers products, - The tools that RAISE will develop can help the industry through targeted and accessible data research, to better identify the risks and lead to economic growth and potential scale-up of businesses.
Publishers	More transparent peer review process, RAI identifier as a new tool of trust for scientific publications, better validation of research results in scientific publications
Open Data Repositories	Can easily adopt RAISE and offer more services, could be linked with other data repositories in the processing layer, without the need for moving datasets, innovative way for FAIR data sharing
Policy makers	RAISE will develop the necessary tools and will provide insightful visual analytics (T4.X) on research data sharing and processing and hence provide the opportunity to policy to foster decision-making processes and policies on data sharing and privacy.
EOSC community	Uptake by the EOSC community and contribution towards long-term sustainability of resources, RAISE is scalable and can grow fast, allowing an increasing volume of research data without constraints, additional EOSC services can be supported by the community crowdsourced network

Table 11: Expected Impact per Key Stakeholders Category

4.5 Partners Individual Exploitation Plan

The consortium is comprised of prestigious organizations with well-established network, know-how and expertise that ensure the necessary visibility and utilization of RAISE results beyond the project's completion. The sub-sections that follow have clustered the project partners into **two categories**, the **research centres / academia** and the **private sector** ones, where the individual exploitation plans along with the strategy to be followed per each is outlined.

4.5.1 Research Centres / Academia partners

The **research centres / academia partners** of the RAISE consortium have sketched up their individual exploitations plans and strategy to follow. The aims of their exploitation strategy are:

- a) to promote the **wider use** of the **output** of the academic research, teaching and services; hence to contribute to wealth creation and quality of life;
- b) to enhance the **academic research** standing and the opportunities for its staff and students;

- c) to generate **additional income** to support the academic activities,
- d) to provide the space for **interinstitutional** and **multidisciplinary cooperations**.

Academic partners will take great advantage from RAISE mainly in terms of: **i)** increased technical know-how and scientific knowledge; **ii)** seamless access to data assets and analysis services, **iii)** increased visibility in the scientific community and proper accreditation of their outputs; **iv)** increased expertise, exploitable for academic purpose.

Based on its focus on research, **RAISE** will extensively focus on **publishing latest findings** in academic conferences and journals. **Project publications** will be one of the most important mechanisms for ensuring that the insights gained from research in the project, especially through the use cases, will be taken up and used in other contexts. It is important to ensure that project's **scientific contribution** will be appraised and replicated by the scientific community, as the project is mainly targeted and will be exploited by them. The engagement of the project with the **scientific community** will be extensive through the publications in **academic journals** and the **presentations** at conferences, thus, ensuring the further utilisation of the project findings by **scientists**.

Research Centres / Academia of RAISE consortium: AUTH, VICOM, UOWM, UOM, SOTON, KI, ATHENA, UHASSELT, EUCENTRE, MCGILL, CERTH, OPENAIR

4.5.2 Private sector partners

A main exploitation modality for **private sector partners** concerns the exploitation of the project's results to **improve the quality of their technology offerings** or even to **build new integrated solutions** that harness the research and validation activities carried out in the project. They will expand their network and **commercially exploit** the project outcomes, by offering new consulting services, further targeting the needs of the market and exploiting the data assets to support and enhance their services. As well as the use of open-source knowledge of the services for 3rd party application. This will allow them to increase their customer base and revenues and in addition enlarge their network of relevant stakeholders, creating a larger visibility of their companies and the potential of new collaborations and expansions of their activities.

Private sector partners of RAISE consortium: INTRA, TCR, WITA, VIL, INNOV, CLPT, AINIGMA, EnvE.X

4.6 Pathway to RAISE Sustainability

The pathway to RAISE sustainability is comprised by a **series of analyses** and **hypothesis** to be produced by the project partners based on the available information from the internal and external environment of the project; the **strategic decisions** to be made that shall comply with the set exploitation objectives and the undertaken actions per se.

Throughout the project's lifetime and in regular intervals the consortium will:

1. co-design the **individual exploitation plans** and **sustainable models** for ensuring further enhancements of all RAISE outputs;
2. make dedicated analysis on the **use case scenarios** and **benefits** for the various stakeholder categories, to be used as a marketing tool;
3. create a **roadmap** for expanding further RAISE main outputs;
4. create a **replication guidebook** to support the reproducibility of services and data assets and
5. receive consultation and verification through the stakeholders' community.

For achieving long term sustainability of project's results, a common strategy will be set up for maximizing the RAISE service impact, aligned with the strategy of EOSC, but also plans for individual exploitable outputs will also be sketched up for enabling partners to potential commercialise their part individually.

4.6.1 Exploitation and Sustainability Planned Actions

Within WP6, under the coordination of **WP6 leader** and the contribution of all **RAISE partners** (*academia and private sector*) the following actions are planned to be performed:

- Clear definition of **Key Exploitable results**.
- Identification of **previously existing software modules** and **running services** in EOSC, to avoid development duplication.
- Discussions with **EOSC** to be arranged on **service sustainability** to ensure RAISE best fit within EOSC.
- Update partners' **individual exploitation plans** that will be based on their contributions and interests within the project that would comply with their organization's strategy.
- **Business Model** creation for RAISE solution as a **whole** and its **financial plan** (*sustainability plan*).
- **Business Model** creation for **individual assets** for exploitation.
- **Registry** creation of the foreground knowledge produced to protect partners' intellectual property rights. Also, aspects of **joint ownerships** to be discussed and agreement to be sought.
- Development of a **legal entity** where all project foreground knowledge will be transferred for commercial exploitation.
- Development of a **Business Plan** that the legal entity will use in order to reach the market.

4.6.2 Timeline and Techniques to be Employed

The RAISE consortium will achieve the planned activities listed in **4.6.1 section** by employing at internal level a series of methods, tools and techniques which namely are:

- Organization of **Innovation management workshops** with RAISE partners (*online and physical during the project's meetings*).
- In case of **joint ownership**, organization of **bilateral calls / discussions** with the involved partners in order to **seek agreement**.
- **Regular WP6 telcos** with the participation of all partners for establishing a common language (*terminology*) on the **needed input** and **facilitate the discussion** around the sustainability of RAISE results.
- **Horizon Europe Methodology** for defining Key Exploitable Results.
- **Numerical exercises** for identification of **RAISE solution's costs** (*variable, fixed etc.*).
- **Foreground knowledge registry** and identification of **joint ownership**.
- **SWOT analysis**.
- **PESTLE analysis**.
- **Business Model Canvas** (*Strategyzer*).
- **Lean Canvas** (*Ash Maurya*).

A tentative timeline of actions quarterly divided along with the techniques to be employed is presented in **Table 12**.

WP6 Phases	Project Month	Actual Month	Quarters	Exploitation & Sustainability Actions	Techniques to be Employed
Phase I M7-M18	M7	April 2023	Q3	First approach on defining the RAISE Key Exploitable results	<i>Horizon Europe Methodology, WP6 Telcos and email exchange</i>
	M8	May 2023			
	M9	June 2023			
	M10	July 2023	Q4	Identification of previously existing software modules and running services in EOSC, to avoid development duplication	<i>WP6 Telcos and discussion with EOSC</i>
	M11	August 2023			
	M12	September 2023			
	M13	October 2023	Q5	Partners individual exploitation plans: initial discussion on the results expected to be produced by each during their involvement in the project and possible usage (<i>in respect to their internal policy</i>)	<i>Co-design individual exploitation plans, WP6 Telcos and email exchange</i>
	M14	November 2023			
	M15	December 2023			
	M16	January 2024	Q6	SWOT Analysis Update	<i>WP6 Telcos and email exchange</i>
	M17	February 2024		Introduction to Business Modelling and initial discussion on potential RAISE Business Models	<i>Business Model Canvas, WP6 Telcos</i>
	M18	March 2024		Submission of the deliverable D6.2	-

D6.1 Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Phase II M19- M40	M19	April 2024	Q7	Identification of joint ownership of the foreground knowledge produced. Update of the Registry's information where needed	<i>Registry of foreground knowledge; Innovation Management Workshops (internal) and WP6 Telcos</i>
	M20	May 2024		Organization of bilateral calls / meetings among the involvement partners where joint ownership identified. Agreement will be sought	<i>Email exchange, partners face-to-face meetings (mainly during project general assembly meetings), bilateral online discussions / telcos</i>
	M21	June 2024			
	M22	July 2024	Q8	Business Model creation for individual assets for exploitation	<i>Business Model Canvas Email Exchange, Innovation Management Workshops (internal), project's physical meetings and WP6 Telcos</i>
	M23	August 2024			
	M24	September 2024			
	M25	October 2024	Q9	Business Model creation for RAISE solution as a whole and its financial plan (<i>sustainability plan</i>)	<i>Business Model Canvas; Numerical exercises for identification of RAISE solution costs; Email Exchange, Innovation Management Workshops (internal), project's physical meetings and WP6 Telcos</i>
	M26	November 2024		Finalization of Key Exploitable Results definition	<i>Email exchange with partners, discussions during WP6 Telcos and project's physical meetings</i>
	M27	December 2024			
	M28	January 2025	Q10	Finalization of Business Model for individual assets for exploitation	<i>Business Model Canvas Email Exchange, Innovation Management Workshops (internal), project's physical meetings and WP6 Telcos</i>
M29	February 2025	Finalization of Business Model for RAISE solution as a whole and its financial plan (<i>sustainability plan</i>)		<i>Business Model Canvas; Numerical exercises for identification of RAISE solution costs; Email Exchange, Innovation Management Workshops (internal), project's physical meetings and WP6 Telcos</i>	
M30	March 2025				

D6.1 Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

	M31	April 2025		Development of a Business Plan that the legal entity (to be established) will use in order to reach the market	<i>Lean Canvas; Innovation Management Workshop (internal), WP6 Telcos</i>
	M32	May 2025	Q11	Finalization of joint ownership discussions	<i>Email exchange, partners face-to-face meetings (mainly during project general assembly meetings), bilateral online discussions / telcos</i>
	M33	June 2025			
	M34	July 2025	Q12	PESTLE Analysis	<i>Email exchange with partners, discussions during WP6 Telcos and project's physical meetings</i>
	M35	August 2025			
	M36	September 2025			
	M37	October 2025	Q13	Development of a legal entity where all project foreground knowledge will be transferred for commercial exploitation	<i>Email exchange, partners face-to-face meetings (mainly during project general assembly meetings), bilateral online discussions / telcos</i>
	M38	November 2025		Finalization legal entity's Business Plan	<i>WP6 Telcos; Email exchange</i>
	M39	December 2025			
	M40	January 2026	Q14 (1/3)	Submission of the Deliverable D6.3	-

Table 12: Exploitation Actions Timeline & Techniques

5 Conclusions

This document set the overall communication, dissemination and exploitation plan of the RAISE project. Divided into **two main parts**, the **first part** (*chapter 2 and 3*) was dedicated to **Communication and Dissemination activities** which enclosed the dissemination strategy that the consortium will follow throughout the project's lifecycle and outlined the planned activities from the submission of D6.1 until January 2026 (*project completion*). Moreover, it included methods, tools and channels selected to be employed towards the successful communication and dissemination of the project and its results while clear responsibilities of partners and execution time were defined. The consortium partners expressed their intentions (*via WP6 Questionnaire*) to make the following dissemination and communication activities:

- listed **68 events** for participation (*conferences, workshops, EOSC meetings, symposia, forums, fairs etc.*) where RAISE project can be communicated via face-to-face activities, presentations, papers, posters and booths/stands.
- organize at least **6 RAISE outreach events** (*physical and virtual*) open to stakeholders for engaging them, promoting the project, its objectives and findings;
- identified **16 scientific publication routes** with potential topics proposed in some cases for further reflection and deepen the collaboration amongst the consortium.

The **second part of D6.1** (*chapter 4*) included the **Exploitation Plan** which will direct project partners' related efforts for defining RAISE solution's end users ("*consumers*" of RAISE services) and potential investors ("*buyers*" of RAISE services); determine their needs and meet them where possible via targeted services; specify the RAISE results and examine potential market uptake; define the foreground knowledge produced and protect the intellectual property of RAISE partners (*individually and as a whole*); update partner's individual plans related to the results produced during the project's implementation and owned by them; and overall ensure the sustainability of the RAISE solution in long term (*beyond the completion of the EU funding*). A timeline of Exploitation Actions was prepared and the techniques/methods that will be utilized for achieving them are

- Organization of **Innovation management workshops** with RAISE partners (*online and physical during the project's meetings*)
- **Regular WP6 telcos** with the participation of all partners for establishing a common language (*terminology*) on the **needed input** and **facilitate the discussion** around the sustainability of RAISE results.
- In case of **joint ownership**, organization of **bilateral calls / discussions** with the involved partners in order to **seek agreement**.
- **Horizon Europe methodology** for defining Key Exploitable Results (*KERs*).
- **Numerical exercises** for identification of **RAISE solution's costs** (*variable, fixed etc.*).
- **Foreground knowledge registry** and identification of **joint ownership**.
- **Business Model Canvas** (*Strategyzer*).
- **Lean Canvas** (*Ash Maurya*).
- **SWOT analysis**.
- **PESTLE analysis**.

The successfulness of the presented overall plan is relied upon project partners' active involvement into such activities while constant monitoring of its course and implementation will be made primarily by **WP6 leader** (*VILABS*) and supportively by the **project coordinator** (*AUTH*).

Concluding, it should be stressed that the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan is considered as an adaptive living document.

Annexes

Annex I – Partners’ Communication Channels and Networks

Categories of Channels & networks	Partners’ Communication Channels & Networks	Partner
Website (News section)	UOWM website	UOWM
	UOWM – Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering website	UOWM
	Internet of THings & AppliCations Lab (ITHACA) website	UOWM
	AUTH website	AUTH
	SOTON website	SOTON
	OPENAIRE website	OPENAIRE
	UOM website	UOM
	ATHENA website	ATHENA
	EUCENTRE website	EUCENTRE
	UHASSELT website	UHASSELT
	WITA website	WITA
	ENVE.X website	ENVE.X
	KI website	KI
	AINIGMA website	AINIGMA
	CYCLOPT website	CYCLOPT
	CERTH / Multimodal Data Fusion and Analytics Group website	CERTH
VICOM website	VICOM	
VILABS website	VILABS	
Social Media	Internet of THings & AppliCations Lab (ITHACA) Facebook page	UOWM
	Internet of THings & AppliCations Lab (ITHACA) Twitter account	UOWM
	Internet of THings & AppliCations Lab (ITHACA) LinkedIn	UOWM

	AUTH social media	AUTH
	SOTON social media	SOTON
	OPENAIRE Twitter account	OPENAIRE
	OPENAIRE LinkedIn account	OPENAIRE
	OPENAIRE Facebook account	OPENAIRE
	UOM social media	UOM
	NETCOMPANY social media	INTRA
	UHASSELT Twitter account	UHASSELT
	UHASSELT LinkedIn account	UHASSELT
	WITA LinkedIn account	WITA
	WITA Facebook account	WITA
	KI social media	KI
	AINIGMA social media	AINIGMA
	CYCLOPT social media	CYCLOPT
	CERTH/ITI LinkedIn account	CERTH
	VICOM LinkedIn account	VICOM
	VICOM Twitter account	VICOM
	VILABS LinkedIn account	VILABS
	VILABS Facebook account	VILABS
	VILABS Twitter account	VILABS
Newsletter	UOWM newsletter	UOWM
	SOTON newsletter	SOTON
	OPENAIRE newsletter (reaches out a large user base of approx. 15K)	OPENAIRE
	EUCENTRE newsletter	EUCENTRE
	UHASSELT newsletter	UHASSELT
	KI newsletter	KI
	CYCLOPT newsletter	CYCLOPT

Press Release	SOTON press releases	SOTON
	UHASSELT press releases	UHASSELT
	WITA press releases	WITA
	VICOM press releases	VICOM
	VILABS press releases	VILABS
YouTube	Internet of THings & AppliCations Lab (ITHACA) YouTube channel	UOWM
	AUTH YouTube channel	AUTH
	SOTON YouTube channel	SOTON
	OPENAIRE YouTube channel	OPENAIRE
	VICOM YouTube channel	VICOM
	VILABS YouTube channel	VILABS
Promotional Material	Internet of THings & AppliCations Lab (ITHACA) promotional material (leaflets, brochures)	UOWM
	AUTH promotional material	AUTH
	ENVE.X promotional material	ENVE.X
	CYCLOPT promotional material	CYCLOPT
	VILABS promotional material	VILABS
Ministries, Municipalities, and Policy Makers (in general)	Municipality of Kozani, Greece	UOWM
	NOADs are mobilized by OPENAIRE in more than 37 countries who have links and connections to their national open science stakeholders, including policymakers (<i>Ministries and research funders</i>) and initiatives.	OPENAIRE
	ESFRI delegate of Cyprus who is representing the relevant department in the Ministry for Research, Innovation and Digital Policy.	INNOV-ACTS
	e-IRG delegate of Greece who is in contact with the ministry of Research in Greece	INNOV-ACTS
	Hellenic Open Science Initiative (HOSI)	INNOV-ACTS
	Spanish/Basque Country health-related cluster (<i>Ametic, Basque health Cluster, Asebio</i>)	VICOM
Mass Media	SVD newspaper	KI

	Dagens Nyheter	<i>KI</i>
Industry	Contact with Industry through Web Science Institute	<i>SOTON</i>
	Big Data Value Association (BDV)	<i>VICOM</i>
Universities and Research Centres	GRNET – National Infrastructures for Research and Technology	<i>UOWM</i>
	University of Pavia	<i>EUCENTRE</i>
	KUL university	<i>AINIGMA</i>
	Cyprus Institute	<i>INNOV-ACTS</i>
	University of Cyprus	<i>INNOV-ACTS</i>
	CYNET (<i>Cypriot NREN</i>)	<i>INNOV-ACTS</i>
Open Data Repositories and National Data Services (NDSs)	HELIX – Hellenic data service	<i>UOWM</i>
	Through PROVIDE service thousands content providers, included, data repositories and national data services can be reached out	<i>OPENAIRE</i>
Other EU funded projects	VITALISE H2020	<i>AUTH, WITA, VILABS, VICOM</i>
	LifeChamps	<i>AUTH</i>
	GILL H2020	<i>AUTH, VILABS</i>
	Urbanome	<i>AUTH</i>
	DIOPTRA	<i>TECREANDO</i>
	BIO-STREAMS	<i>TECREANDO</i>
	iDREAMS EU Horizon	<i>UHASSELT</i>
	S&R EU Horizon	<i>UHASSELT</i>
	OBERON	<i>ENVE.X</i>
	URBANOME	<i>ENVE.X</i>
	EJP project PARC	<i>ENVE.X</i>
	AI Prognosis	<i>AINIGMA</i>
	FAIR	<i>AINIGMA</i>

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	e-IRG and ESFRI support projects	<i>INNOV-ACTS</i>
	HEU SYNTHEMA	<i>VICOM</i>
	HEU FORCEREPAIR	<i>VICOM</i>
	HEU LUCIA (<i>Cancer mission</i>)	<i>VICOM</i>

Annex II – Action Plan [Detailed List]

Activity	Description	Involved Partner / s
Participation to a third party event <i>(i.e. conference exhibition, forum, symposium, meetings)</i>	Open Science Conference When: 27-29 Sep. 2023 Where: Online More at: https://www.open-science-conference.eu/	Plan to participate: ATHENA, Intention / interest expression: AUTH, OPENAIRE, UOM, INTRA, EUCENTRE, UHASSELT. ENVE.X, KI, VICOM
	Open Science FAIR When: 25-27 September 2023 Where: Madrid, Spain More at: https://www.opensciencefair.eu/	Plan to participate: OPENAIRE Intention / interest expression: AUTH, ATHENA, TECREANDO, INNOV-ACTS, UOM
	19th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations When: 14 -17 June 2023 Where: Leon, Spain & Hybrid More at: https://ifipaiai.org/2023/	Plan to participate: ATHENA, TECREANDO, CERTH Intention / interest expression: UOWM, ENVE.X, AINIGMA, CYCLOPT
	AIAI Conferences of 2024 and / or 2025 (upcoming) When: TBD Where: TBD More at (when available): https://ifipaiai.org/	Plan to participate: TECREANDO, CYCLOPT Intention / interest expression: ATHENA, INTRA, KI, VICOM, UOM
	International Conference on Recent Innovations in Computer Science, Engineering and Technology When: 2-3 December 2023 Where: Scotland, UK More at: http://scienceplus.us/Conference/25698/ICRICSET/	Plan to participate: KI Intention / interest expression: UOWM, ATHENA, UHASSELT
	26th European Conference on Artificial Intelligence When: 30 Sept. - 5 Oct. 2023 Where: Krakow, Poland More at: https://ecai2023.eu/	Plan to participate: TECREANDO, KI Intention / interest expression: UOWM, AUTH, SOTON, ATHENA, EUCENTRE, ENVE.X, AINIGMA, CYCLOPT
	International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (upcoming 2024, 2025) When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://www.ijcai.org/future_conferences	Plan to participate: - Intention / interest expression: SOTON, ATHENA, TECREANDO, EUCENTRE, ENVE.X, KI, AINIGMA, CYCLOPT, UOM
	Big Data Conference Europe When: 21 - 24 November 2023 Where: TBD More at: https://bigdataconference.eu/2022/index.html	Plan to participate: KI, CYCLOPT Intention / interest expression: UOWM, SOTON, TECREANDO,

		EUCENTRE, UHASSELT, ENVE.X, CERTH, UOM
	International Data Week 2023 When: 23 - 26 October 2023 Where: Salzburg, Austria More at: https://internationaldataweek.org/	Plan to participate: OPENAIRE, KI Intention / interest expression: SOTON, ATHENA, TECREANDO, CYCLOPT, INNOV-ACTS, CERTH
	SciDataCon 2023 When: 23-26 October 2023 More at: https://www.scidatacon.org/	Plan to participate: OPENAIRE Intention / interest expression: AUTH, ATHENA, TECREANDO, KI, INNOV-ACTS
	DATUM (upcoming 2024 and / or 2025) When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://datum23.csd.auth.gr/	Plan to participate: - Intention / interest expression: KI
	Medical Informatics Europe (upcoming 2024 and / or 2025) When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://www.mie2023.org/	Plan to participate: AUTH Intention / interest expression: ATHENA, EUCENTRE, WITA, KI,
	Innovation for Health (upcoming 2024, 2025) When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://www.hyphenprojects.nl/i4h	Plan to participate: - Intention / interest expression: AUTH, ATHENA, ENVE.X, KI
	DMEA Exhibition (upcoming 2024, 2025) When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://www.dmea.de/en/	Plan to participate: - Intention / interest expression: ATHENA, INTRA
	MED TECH INNOVATION EXPO (upcoming 2024, 2025) When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://med-techexpo.com/	Plan to participate: - Intention / interest expression: AUTH, ATHENA, WITA
	International Conference on Driver Behavior Analysis (upcoming 2024, 2025) When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://waset.org/driver-behavior-analysis-conference-in-july-2023-in-rome	Plan to participate: KI Intention / interest expression: TECREANDO
	World Conference on Transport Research (upcoming 2024, 2025) When: TBD Where: TBD More at: http://wctr2023.ca/	Plan to participate: UHASSELT Intention / interest expression: INTRA
	INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS ON TRANSPORTATION RESEARCH (upcoming 2024, 2025)	Plan to participate: UHASSELT, KI, CERTH

	<p>When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://www.ictr.gr/</p>	<p>Intention / interest expression: ATHENA, INTRA</p>
	<p>Annual POLIS Conference (upcoming 2024, 2025) When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://www.polisnetwork.eu/2023-annual-polis-conference/</p>	<p>Plan to participate: UHASSELT, KI Intention / interest expression: ENVE.X</p>
	<p>European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving (EUCAD) When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/blog/eucad2023/</p>	<p>Plan to participate: - Intention / interest expression: UHASSELT</p>
	<p>ITS European Congress <i>(upcoming 2024, 2025)</i> When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://itseuropeancongress.com/contribute-and-submit-your-proposal-for-its-lisbon-2023/</p>	<p>Plan to participate: UHASSELT, VICOM Intention / interest expression: TECREANDO, ENVE.X, CERTH</p>
	<p>SMART CITIES SYMPOSIUM <i>(upcoming 2024, 2025)</i> When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://akce.fd.cvut.cz/en/scsp2023</p>	<p>Plan to participate: - Intention / interest expression: UOWM, SOTON, UOM, INTRA, TECREANDO, EUCENTRE, UHASSELT, ENVE.X, CERTH</p>
	<p>RDA-EOSC event When: 20 March 2023 Where: Gothenburg, Sweden More at: https://www.rd-alliance.org/save-date-global-research-commons-europe-and-beyond</p>	<p>Plan to participate: OPENAIRE, KI, INNOV-ACTS Intention / interest expression: TECREANDO</p>
	<p>RDA 20th plenary meeting When: 21-23 March 2023 Where: Gothenburg, Sweden More at: https://www.eosc.eu/events/rda-20th-plenary-gothenburg-research-data-alliance-10th-anniversary</p>	<p>Plan to participate: OPENAIRE Intention / interest expression: INNOV-ACTS</p>
	<p>EuroHPC Summit 2023 When: 20-23 March 2023 Where: Gothenburg, Sweden More at: https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/events/eurohpc-summit-2023-2023-03-20_en</p>	<p>Plan to participate: KI, INNOV-ACTS Intention / interest expression: UOM</p>
	<p>6th EOSC General Assembly <i>(only for EOSC-A members)</i> When: 22-23 May 2023 Where: Brussels, Belgium More at: https://eosc.eu/events/eosc-general-assembly-6</p>	<p>Plan to participate: AUTH, KI Intention / interest expression: -</p>

	<p>TNC2023 When: 5-9 June 2023 Where: Tirana, Albania More at: https://tnc23.geant.org/about/</p>	<p>Plan to participate: - Intention / interest expression: INNOV-ACTS</p>
	<p>The potential of Research Data When: 19-20 June 2023 Where: Lund, Sweden</p>	<p>Plan to participate: INNOV-ACTS Intention / interest expression: UOM</p>
	<p>e-IRG 20 years anniversary event When: 22-23 June 2023 Where: Lund, Sweden</p>	<p>Plan to participate: INNOV-ACTS Intention / interest expression: KI,</p>
	<p>EGI2023 conference When: 19-23 June Where: Poznan, Poland More at: https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023/</p>	<p>Plan to participate: - Intention / interest expression: AUTH, OPENAIRE, CYCLOPT, INNOV-ACTS</p>
	<p>ESFRI Stakeholders Forum and RI event When: 27-29 September, Where: Tenerife, Spain</p>	<p>Plan to participate: INNOV-ACTS Intention / interest expression: ENVE.X, KI, CYCLOPT</p>
	<p>EOSC Symposium 2023 When: 18-22 September 2023 Where: TBC, Spain</p>	<p>Plan to participate: OPENAIRE, INNOV-ACTS Intention / interest expression: AUTH, SOTON, UOM, KI, CYCLOPT, VICOM</p>
	<p>EOSC Symposium 2024 When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p>Plan to participate: OPENAIRE, INNOV-ACTS Intention / interest expression: AUTH, SOTON, UOM, KI, CYCLOPT, VICOM</p>
	<p>EUDAT event 2023 When: TBD Where: TBD More at: https://eudat.eu/events</p>	<p>Plan to participate: - Intention / interest expression: SOTON, OPENAIRE, KI, INNOV-ACTS</p>
	<p>South Eastern European Design Automation, Computer Engineering, Computer Networks and Social Media Conference (SEEDA-CECNSM) When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p>Plan to participate: UOWM</p>
	<p>International Conference on Emerging Trends In Engineering and Technology (ICETET) When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p>Plan to participate: UOWM</p>
	<p>IEEE ICC: IEEE International Conference on Communications</p>	<p>Plan to participate: UOWM</p>

Participation to a third party event <i>(i.e. conference exhibition, forum, symposium, meetings)</i>	When: TBD Where: TBD	
	IEEE Global Communications Conference When: TBD Where: TBD	<u>Plan to participate:</u> UOWM
	IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications When: TBD Where: TBD	<u>Plan to participate:</u> UOWM
	CBMS 2023 When: TBD Where: TBD	<u>Plan to participate:</u> AUTH
	IEEE BSN23 When: TBD Where: TBD	<u>Plan to participate:</u> AUTH
	26th International Conference on Extending Database Technology (EDBT 2023) When: 28th March - 31st March, 2023 Where: Ioannina, Greece	<u>Plan to participate:</u> SOTON
	Symposium on AI, Data and Digitalization (SSAID 2023) When: May 9-10, 2023 Where: Sognadal, Norway	<u>Plan to participate:</u> SOTON
	BDVA Data Week 2023, When: 13-15 June 2023 Where: Lulea, Sweden,	<u>Plan to participate:</u> SOTON
	ACM SIGMOD/PODS International Conference on Management of Data 2023 When: TBD Where: TBD	<u>Plan to participate:</u> SOTON
	International Semantic Web Conference When: TBD Where: TBD	<u>Plan to participate:</u> OPENAIRE
	RDA P21 in Austria When: TBD	<u>Plan to participate:</u> OPENAIRE

	<p>6th International Conference on Technical Debt 2023, When: 14-15 May 2023, Where: Melbourne, Australia,</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> UOM</p>
<p>16th International Conference on the Quality of Information and Communications Technology When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> UOM</p>	
<p>International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering 2024 When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> UOM</p>	
<p>International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> UOM</p>	
<p>International Conference on Software Architecture When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> UOM</p>	
<p>Human Brain Project Summit When: Marseille, France Where: 28-31 March, 2023</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> ATHENA</p>	
<p>MESAEP Symposium When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> EUCENTRE</p>	
<p>TRB 2024 Annual Meeting When: 7-11 January 2024 Where: Washington DC, USA More at: https://www.trb.org/AnnualMeeting/FutureDates.aspx</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> UHASSELT</p>	
<p>ICASSP When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> AINIGMA</p>	
<p>EUSIPCO When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> AINIGMA</p>	

	<p>EMBC When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> AINIGMA</p>
	<p>Mining Software Repositories 2023 / 2024 / 2025 When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> CYCLOPT</p>
	<p>International Conference on Software Engineering 2023 / 2024 / 2025 When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> CYCLOPT</p>
	<p>Fundamental aspects on Software Engineering 2023 / 2024 / 2025 When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> CYCLOPT</p>
	<p>The International Workshop on Artificial Intelligence in Medicine & Healthcare Technical”- AIMH 2023 When: 12 -15 June 2023 Where: Portoroz, Slovenia</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> CERTH</p>
	<p>The 24th Conference on Control Systems and Computer Science (CSCS24 2023), When: 24-26 May 2023 Where: Bucharest, Romania, More at: https://cscs24.hpc.pub.ro</p>	<p><u>Plan to participate:</u> CERTH</p>
	<p>Open Science services and EOSC in Greece – Vol.2 Where: Kozani, Greece When: End of April 2023, Description: The workshop aims at exchanging knowledge and experiences on how to better coordinate among all national actors who contribute to EOSC and how to empower the Greek research community with Open Science best practices, applicable in the European Research Area and the Horizon Europe.</p>	<p><u>Plan to organize RAISE event:</u> UOWM, AUTH Involvement / contribution: <i>all RAISE partners, External Researchers from UOWM</i></p>
	<p>RAISE Requirements Capture Event [WP2] When: TBD Where: TBD</p>	<p><u>Plan to organize RAISE event:</u> INNOV-ACTS, WP2 partners</p>

Organization of project's event	<p>1st RAISE Datathon – Online event [WP2, WP6]</p> <p>When: TBD</p> <p>Description: engage external researchers in the RAISE community while testing the RAISE system</p>	<p>Plan to organize RAISE event: VILABS</p> <p>Involvement / contribution: INNOV-ACTS, AUTH, ATHENA, OPENAIRE, VICOM, CERTH-HIT, KI, UHASSELT, EUCENTRE, EnvE.X, AINIGMA, McGill</p>
	<p>2nd RAISE Datathon – Online event [WP2, WP6]</p> <p>When: TBD</p> <p>Description: engage external researchers in the RAISE community while testing the RAISE system</p>	<p>Plan to organize RAISE event: VILABS</p> <p>Involvement / contribution: INNOV-ACTS, AUTH, ATHENA, OPENAIRE, VICOM, CERTH-HIT, KI, UHASSELT, EUCENTRE, EnvE.X, AINIGMA, McGill</p>
	<p>3rd RAISE Datathon – Online event [WP2, WP6]</p> <p>When: TBD</p> <p>Description: Engage external researchers in the RAISE community while testing the RAISE system</p>	<p>Plan to organize RAISE event: VILABS</p> <p>Involvement / contribution: INNOV-ACTS, AUTH, ATHENA, OPENAIRE, VICOM, CERTH-HIT, KI, UHASSELT, EUCENTRE, EnvE.X, AINIGMA, McGill</p>
	<p>RAISE Final Conference</p> <p>When: TBD – approx.. the final 3 months of project's implementation</p> <p>Where: TBD</p> <p>Description: Disseminate the major outcomes of the project</p>	<p>Plan to organize RAISE event: AUTH, VILABS and the rest of the consortium</p>
Publications	<p>26th International Conference on Extending Database Technology 2023 (EDBT 2023),</p> <p>When: 28th March - 31st March 2023</p> <p>Where Ioannina, Greece,</p> <p>Topic: "Consent Management for Data Processing Workflows: A Graph Problem"</p>	SOTON
	<p>Symposium on AI, Data and Digitalization (SSAID 2023),</p> <p>When: May 9-10, 2023</p> <p>Where Sognadal, Norway,</p> <p>Topic: "Data Marketplaces in the AI Economy"</p>	SOTON
	<p>BDVA Data Week 2023,</p> <p>When: 13-15 June 2023</p> <p>Where Lulea, Sweden,</p> <p>Topic: TBD</p>	SOTON

	Event TBD, Topic: RAI Concept paper <i>(all partners contribution to be requested)</i>	AUTH
	Event TBD, Topic: Results from Health pilot (T5.2) with main contribution by the related partners will be requested	AUTH
	Event TBD, Topic: Integration of RAISEids and repository/catalogue with ARGOS	OPENAIRE
	6th International Conference on Technical Debt 2023, When: 14-15 May 2023, Where Melbourne, Australia, Topic: Exploring the Effect of Various Maintenance Activities on the Accumulation of TD Principal	UOM
	Elsevier Internet of Things Journal Topic: TBD	UOWM
	IEEE Transactions on Networking Journal Topic: TBD	UOWM
	Elsevier Computer Networks Journal Topic: TBD	UOWM
	Journal of Medical Internet Research, MDPI Topic: Holistic Health Records and the potential of AI	KI
	EMBC Conference Topic: TBD	AINIGMA
	IEEE biomedical engineering Topic: TBD	AINIGMA
	IET Software Journal Topic: TBD	CYCLOPT
	ICSOFT Conference Topic: TBD	CYCLOPT

	<p>Business Model Conference When: TBD Where: TBD Topic: Potential Business Models of RAISE solution based on the results produced in T6.2</p>	VILABS
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Annex III – Dissemination Request Template

Date of request: DD/MM/YYYY

Activity Type: *Insert one type of dissemination activity*

Please choose one of the following types: **conference paper, scientific journal, scientific poster, scientific magazine, book chapter**

Author / s: _____, _____,

Title of Journal / Event / Magazine / Book : _____

Date of the Event : DD/MM/YYYY

Place of the Event (*location*): _____

TITLE: PLEASE INSERT THE PUBLICATION TITLE

ABSTRACT / SHORT SUMMARY	Please insert a short description / abstract
RELATION TO RAISE	Please choose one of the following: <i>Simple reference, concept description, work description, key paper presenting RAISE</i>

Annex IV – Reporting Template of Communication & Dissemination Actions

The template corresponds with the requested information for completion on Sygma (*Participant Portal Grant Management Services*)

Dissemination Activity name	What? <i>Type of dissemination activity*</i>	Who? <i>Target audience Reached*</i>	Why? <i>Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters) *</i>	Status of the dissemination activity*
<p>[Please insert text]</p>	<p>Available Options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferences Education and training events • Meetings • Clustering activities • Collaboration with EU-funded projects • Other scientific cooperation • Other 	<p>Available Options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research communities • Industry, business partners • Innovators • Investors • International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.) • EU Institutions • National authorities • Regional authorities • Local authorities • Civil society • Citizens • Specific end user communities • Other <p>Multiple selection allowed</p>	<p>[Please insert text]</p>	<p>Available Options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cancelled • Delivered • Ongoing • Postponed <p>Please select one (1) option</p>